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Project 1

Above-threshold ionization of 1D hydrogen

FYS4096 - COMPUTATIONAL PHYSICS

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Table of Content

- 1 Introduction** **1**

- 2 Theory** **2**

- 3 Method used** **3**

- 4 Set up and checking** **4**
 - 4.1 Setup 4
 - 4.2 Checking and Convergence 6

- 5 Results** **7**

- 6 Discussion** **8**

- 7 Conclusion** **10**

- References 11

1 Introduction

This report is aimed at analyzing and modeling the interactions between a laser pulse's characteristics and the atoms exposed to its beam.

In order to analyze those relations, we are to consider a system compound of hydrogen atom in 1D, and make several simulations where we will change the laser parameters to observe the effects it has on the distribution probability of the ionized electrons' kinetic energy.

Eventually, we shall prove that most of the electrons' kinetic energy verify the formula for the above-threshold ionization :

$$E_{kin} = n \times \omega_0 - I \tag{1}$$

2 Theory

Let us start with a little bit of theory, shall the reading of the report be clearer.

The experiment we are modeling is a system where atoms of Hydrogen are exposed to a relatively weak laser pulse. The photons that compound this beam then collide with the hydrogen atoms, and as a result, ionize them by transmitting energy to their electrons, which, if this energy is great enough, can free themselves (in other words, for $n\omega_0 > I$).

It is a well known fact that in quantum mechanics and though in atomic world, the energy is quantized, meaning that it can only take specific values. That is what led us to the previous formula that we are trying to demonstrate : That the kinetic energy of the newly free electrons is the difference between the ionization energy of the atom (that keep them close to the nuclei) and the energy given by the photons (that must be an integer multiple of the photons frequency).

The threshold ionization energy (I) is the minimum energy that electrons need to gain, by absorbing n_{min} photons, in order to free themselves from the nuclei's attraction. In our case it corresponds to the inverse of the ground state energy : $I = 13.6eV \approx 0.5u.a.$ Thus when we talk about above threshold ionization energy, we refer to the multi-photon absorption process, where the number of photon absorbed n is superior than n_{min} .

Taking this into account plus considering the conservation of energy among our system, it allows us to measure the kinetic energy distribution of the ionized electrons, supposedly appearing in peaks, separated by ω_0 the irradiating photon energy.

3 Method used

For us to prove that the distribution of energy for the ionized electrons is correlated to the formula 7, we have made our simulations through python programs and Matplotlib visualizations.

First, in order to implement the basis of this modelization, we have used the scripts and documentation from the exercise 6, by Janne Solanpää for the class FYS-4096. These scripts were directly aimed at describing the density of electrons according to the parameters of the laser used, giving out the final wave function for the system after the final propagation time, as well as its Hamiltonian.

Hence, our main task was to write another script, named "density_distri", using the datas obtained, that would calculate the density probability distribution of the energy for these ionized electrons, from the formula :

$$P(E) = \gamma^4 \langle \Psi(t = T_{max}) | [(\mathbf{H}_0 - E)^4 + \gamma^4]^{-1} | \Psi(t = T_{max}) \rangle \omega_0 = 0.2a.u. \quad (2)$$

Taito hasn't been used for the simulations, because they could be handled through the python's program. Also every calculus has been made in atomic units, so that our laser's characteristics are the following :

$$T_{max} = \frac{36 \times 10^{-15}}{2.4188843 \times 10^{-17}} = 1488a.u.$$

$$\omega_0 = 0.2a.u.$$

$$E_{max} = 0.06a.u.$$

4 Set up and checking

4.1 Setup

In order for the code to run properly, time scale, energies, as well as energy spacing were to be set.

Based on the formula we wanted to demonstrate, on calculation and on several simulations, the energy range, on which we were to evaluate the density probability has been set on [0:1] a.u., to spot the first peaks, and [0:14] a.u. to appreciate the global form of the curve.

To get those results, we used the formula 7, and our knowledge about the above threshold ionization theory to calculate n_{min} and though the location of the peaks.

$$n_{min} = \frac{I}{\omega_0} = \frac{0.5}{0.2} \approx 3 \quad (3)$$

(because must be an integer)

Once this range was determined, γ had to be set. It was allegedly half of the energy spacing. After testing different values we decided to give it the one of 0.0125, because if it was to be too big, it was merely impossible to see any of the expected peak for the distribution energy, and if it was too small, there were too much noise on the graph, hindering our analysis of the spectra . Also, the graph has been plot in logarithm scale along the y axis, because the distribution follows a power-law form, which a logarithm shape fits better.

Figure 1: Graph plot with $\gamma=1$

Figure 2: Graph plot with $\gamma = 0.0125$

The difference between the two graphs is explained by the fact that γ stands for the so-called Keldysh parameter. The bigger it gets, the lower the chances are for the electron to tunnel through its potential barrier and thus get ionized. That agrees perfectly with our visualization, because with a bigger γ , no peaks are visible.

4.2 Checking and Convergence

Unit tests were implemented to check if our code was properly working, using wavefunction and Hamiltonian which we already knew the distribution density of energy of.

As we didn't get graphs according to our expectations and that changing the parameters of the laser didn't affect it, the checking and convergence couldn't be evaluated properly. The fluctuations we shall have seen are though discussed in the discussion part of the report.

5 Results

Figure 3: Density probability of energy on a large energy scale

Despite the lack of rightfulness of our graph, as the mistake in the code couldn't be found to be corrected the report has been mainly made on research.

6 Discussion

Figure 4: Density probability of energy and presumed position of its first three above-threshold ionization peaks

First, we can see that even though the density probability of energy rightfully decreases for higher energies, our spectrum disagree with our expectations.

Indeed, we were awaiting for clear peaks where the dashed lines are, corresponding to the absorption of several photons, that do not appear in the graph. The first dashed line should stand for the kinetic Energy for the absorbtion of 3 photons (considering that it is the minimum for the electron to free itself), the second for the absorption of 4 photons, and so on. This difference between our results and expectations leads us to think that there must be an error into our code. This deduction was confirmed by the fact that during our checking, changing the parameters had no effect on the plot. We could then infer that the error must come from the part where Ψ and H_0 are calculated. Since we are lacking actual results from our code, extra research were made in order to see which outcomes we should have obtained.

In a first time, changing the time spacing should have affected the graph in a way that the smaller it is, the most accurate $|\Psi(\mathbf{T}_{max})\rangle$ gets. One could think that, as we only use explicitly Ψ evaluated at \mathbf{T}_{max} , changing Δt wouldn't affect our results. However, as the wavefunction's calculation relies on Δt , its variation must have an impact on the quality of its evaluation. Then, concerning the intensity of the electric field of the laser, in other word its amplitude, as the ionisation's rate of the electrons is directly proportional to $(E_{max})^{n_{min}}$, we can affirm that either by increasing the field's intensity or decreasing its frequency (because the lower ω_0 gets, the higher n_{min} is) can reduce the time for the electrons' ionization to take place.

Then, another consequence of changing the laser's frequency would be a shift of the above threshold ionization peaks, because their localisation and the spacing between them relies directly on the value for ω_0 . Finally, we know that variating the number of point of the grid affects the quality of the electron's density, and so, as it gets greater, it must result a finer density probability of energy graph, because it is explicitly relied to the electron's coordinate.

7 Conclusion

We can conclude that, even though our visualization wasn't up to our expectations, the proof of the equation teach us something. The fact that electrons could absorb more photons that needed to get ionized is in contradiction with the principle wanting that electrons in free space shouldn't be able to absorb photons. Though, the Above Threshold Ionization has proved that, for an electron in presence of the same field than the one its original atom was exposed to, the absorption of several photons was actually possible, and still satisfied the momentum conservation law.

References

1. Solanpää, J. (2018). Course Material FYS-4096: Computational Physics. *exercise 6*.
2. Pullen, M.G.(2011). Above threshold ionization of atomic Hydrogen using few-cycle pulses. (Doctoral dissertation).Retrived from https://www120.secure.griffith.edu.au/rch/file/bbfdefcd-7b14-fc22-c24f-e46c4f88d4b7/1/Pullen_2011_02Thesis.pdf.
3. Rivarola, R. D., Fainstein, P. D., Lima, M. A. P., (2006). Photonic, Electronic And Atomic Collisions - Proceedings Of The Xxiv International Conference. *Ionization by short UV Laser Pulses: Secondary ATI peaks of the electron spectrum*.